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An overview of Sri Lanka cement industry: Environmental impacts, methodologies and mitigation measures

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The cement industry plays a conspicuous role in world industries. It distributes throughout the world as a result of an abundance of raw materials.

Cement as far as we might be concerned was first evolved by Joseph Aspdin, an ambitious nineteenth-century British stonemason, who warmed a blend of ground limestone and mud in his kitchen oven, then at that point, pummeled the invention into a fine powder. The outcome was the world's first hydraulic cement, one that solidifies when water is added.

In the modern world, cement is an important thing in side of building construction. There are no building construction outcomes without it. There are alternatives for cement. But cement is still dominant as a result of its physical and chemical properties. The properties are fineness, soundness, strength, setting time, heat of hydration, loss of ignition, bulk density and specific gravity, etc. The fineness means particle size in cement. Hydration occurs in cement. Hydrations depend on particle size. When the particle size is small, the area-to-volume ratio increases, as a result of it, there is more area available for water molecules. Hydration occurs very quickly, and it supports strength and durability.

The soundness refers back to the capacity of a hardened cement paste to maintain its volume after setting without not no time expansion. This expansion is a result of immoderate quantities of unfastened lime (CaO) or magnesia (MgO).

The time required for setting cement paste is referred to as setting time. The number of factors affect setting time. Those are fineness, water-cement ratio, chemical content, and admixtures. There are two types of setting times defined. Those are the initial setting and final setting. The initial setting occurs when the paste starts to become rigid. Final setting time is defined as rigidity enough to load something. In other words, it can be defined as the time taken to hard to load something.

Cement paste strength is normally described in 3 ways; Compressive, tensile, and flexural. Number of factors that affect the strength of cement. Those are water-cement ratio, cement-pleasant combination ratio, type and grading of fine aggregate, curing situations, etc. When water is added to cement, hydration occurs and produces heat. It affects the quality of cement and is beneficial to manipulate at a cool temperature.

The heating of a cement sample at 900-1000 °C causes weight loss. This weight loss refers to loss of ignition.

When water is added to cement, it replaced the air-filled areas. And cement shows 2.90 – 3.15 specific gravity.

The chemical properties depend on its composition. Four main components can be observed in cement. Those are belite, alite, celite and brownmillerite.

- Dicalcium Silicate / Belite $2\text{CaO}.\text{SiO}_2$
- Tricalcium Silicate / Alite $3\text{CaO}.\text{SiO}_2$
- Tricalcium Aluminate / Celite $3\text{CaO}.\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$
- Brownmillerite $4\text{CaO}.\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3.\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$

As a result, four types of Oxides can be observed in cement. Those are CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃. MgO, SO₃, K₂O, and NaO are also contained in less amounts.

As a result of these chemical and physical properties cement is widely used in construction. There are two types of cement according to the ability of the cement to set in the presence of water. Those are hydraulic cement and non-hydraulic cement.

The chemical reaction between dry ingredients and water forms an adhesive substance in hydraulic cement. Hydraulic cement is less soluble in water. As a result, they are quite durable and show less chemical attacks. Hydraulic cement is made out of belite, alite, celite, and brownmillerite. Celite (Tricalcium Aluminate) and brownmillerite play an essential role in the formation of the sintering.

Non-hydraulic cement is not in wet conditions or underwater. They are set as a result of a reaction with atmospheric carbon dioxide. CaO produced from CaCO₃ (lime) reacts with water, and produced Ca(OH)₂ (Slaked lime). This Ca(OH)₂ reacts with atmospheric CO₂, and produces CaCO₃ again. This whole process is referred to as the lime cycle. The steps involved in this reaction can be illustrated as below,

The non-hydraulic cement is not composed of belite, alite, celite, and brownmillerite. They are composed of lime (CaO), gypsum (CaSO₄) plaster. Belite, alite, celite and brownmillerite are not necessary for non-hydraulic cement, because there is no hydration reaction involved in the setting. Non-hydraulic cement setting as a result of carbonation.

When we talk about cement, hydraulic cement comes to our mind. It is normal because hydraulic cement is widely used in construction fields worldwide. And I mentioned the properties of cement in this article, related to hydraulic cement. As a result of the chemical reactivity of non-hydraulic cement and the long-time requirement for setting, non-hydraulic cement is not used in giant construction in the modern world. But most historical constructions were built using non-hydraulic cement such as lime mortar.

The disadvantage of non-hydraulic cement, hydraulic cement is widely used in the construction field.

This hydraulic cement is typically referred to as Portland cement. The name Portland is because of the resemblance of the cement when set to Portland stone. Portland cement is defined as a hydraulic cement produced by pulverizing clinker consisting essentially of hydraulic calcium silicate, usually containing one or more of the forms of calcium sulfate as an inter-ground addition.

Portland cement is composed of the number of oxides. Those are CaO 64% , Al₂O₃ 5.5%, Fe₂O₃ 3%, SiO₂ 22%, MgO 1.4% and SO₃ 2.1%.

This cement is produced by heating limestone (CaCO₃) with other materials such as clay, shale, and Iron ore to 1450 °C in a kiln, in a process known as calcination, whereby a molecular

carbon dioxide is liberated from calcium carbonate to form calcium oxide quicklime. These calcium oxides react with other oxides such as Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , and Fe_2O_3 in clay and form Belite, Alite, Celite, and Brownmillerite like other ingredients. The resulting substance is referred to as clinker ground with a small amount of gypsum to produce ordinary Portland cement.

The four steps are involved in the preparation of cement. Those are,

1. Acquisition of raw materials
2. Preparation of raw materials
3. Burning
4. Addition of gypsum and distributions

The raw materials of Portland cement are limestone, shale, marl, sand, clay, slag, iron ore, and mill scale. The constituents of these raw materials form components of cement during burning. Limestone, shale, and marl are usually used as calcium sources for cement. Iron ore, clay, and mill scale are used as iron oxide sources for cement. Some raw materials are used as more than one source, because they are composed of a number of constituents.

There are two methods to follow in cement manufacturing. Those are the wet process and the dry process. But the final result is the same. In the dry process limestone and clay are separately ground and mix them according to the correct ratio. In the wet process, raw materials are pulverized and dissolved in water using a ball mill. At that time the liquid mixture of raw material was referred to as slurry. This liquid mixture which is slurry is stored in the tank known as silos. In silos, slurry adjusts to correct proportions. Corrected slurry after feeding into the rotary kiln. Actually, both processes do something that is mixing and grounding raw materials. But its manner is little bit different. The final product of both processes feeds into the kiln.

In the cement industry, a rotary kiln is used. It rotates around the axis, and it is at an angle. The upper opening is used to feed it. From the bottom, the clinker is removed. Coal, oil, or natural gas are used to produce a flame in the kiln. As a result of the flame, the temperature of the kiln extends to $25^\circ\text{C} - 1500^\circ\text{C}$. With temperature variation inside the kiln, different changes occur in raw materials. To 700°C raw materials are free-flowing powder. Water is lost from raw materials under this temperature. Under $700^\circ\text{C} - 900^\circ\text{C}$ temperature powder is still free flowing. Calcination occurs and CaO is produced under this temperature and the formation of dicalcium silicate begins at this temperature. Under $1150^\circ\text{C} - 1200^\circ\text{C}$ temperature belite (dicalcium silicate) crystals are formed and particles start to get sticky. under $1200^\circ\text{C} - 1350^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range, a liquid phase is formed. Liquid allows reaction between belite and free CaO to form alite. The particle starts to agglomerate. Under the $1350^\circ\text{C} - 1450^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range, the amount of belite crystals is decreased and their size is increased. The number of alite and size increase under this temperature range. Within cooling, this mixture of tricalcium aluminate and tetracalcium aluminoferrite is formed. This fusion of ingredients together, chemically without melting is referred to as sintering. And its product is referred to as clinker. After, this clinker is mixed with 4% gypsum and ground together, and packed to distribute. This final product is referred to as cement. Actually, Portland cement.

By changing the amount of raw materials, we can produce different types of Portland cement such as rapid hardening Portland cement, quick setting Portland cement, white Portland cement, waterproofed Portland cement, Hydrophobic Portland cement, low heat Portland cement, sulfate resisting Portland cement, Kuhl Portland cement, Iron ore cement or Erz cement, Ferrari cement, expanding or non – shrinking cement and air entraining cement.

Rapid hardening cement is similar to ordinary Portland cement, but it develops strength more rapidly. The composition of rapid hardening cement is a bit different from ordinary Portland cement and the ground finer. As a result of finer particles this cement rapidly hardens.

The quick setting Portland cement is different from ordinary Portland cement as a result of less setting time. The rate of gain of strength is similar to ordinary Portland cement. The quick setting cement is composed of less amount of gypsum compared to ordinary Portland cement. As a result of these quick settings, they are used in underwater constructions.

White Portland cement is an iron or manganese-free cement type. Chalk and iron-free clay (China clay) is used as the main ingredient in this cement. Oil fuel and coal are not used to produce a flame in the kiln. Therefore, white Portland cement production is much more expensive than ordinary cement production.

Waterproof cement is the name given to Portland cement by the property of water repellent. That property is given by grinding a small proportion of calcium stearate or of a non-saponifiable oil.

Hydrophobic cement is manufactured by grinding clinker with water-repellent film substances such as oleic acid, stearic acid, etc. these water-repellent substances form a layer around the cement particles, and as a result, it doesn't allow water to mix.

Low-heat Portland cement is produced by chemical modification. This type of cement varies from normal Portland cement as a result of its composition. The tricalcium aluminate percentage is lower than ordinary Portland cement and a higher percentage in dicalcium silicate. The benefits of low-temperature cement are, it helps to minimize the risk of thermal cracking in thick sections of concrete, Improved durability performance, excellent performance, such as high ultimate strength, sulfate corrosion resistance, good lasting properties, good fracture toughness, and anti-leakage. It is poured into hydraulic concrete and ship-concrete plants. Significantly improved later-age concrete strengths. Resistance to sulfate attack in the reinforcement, mainly in concrete pipes. The disadvantages of low-heat Portland cement are that cement can't be used in cold weather. The cost of cement is higher than that of ordinary Portland cement.

The sulfate aluminates are very expansive as a result of them causing maximum damage to concrete structures. Therefore, sulfate-resisting Portland cement is used in sulfate abundant areas. The amount of tricalcium aluminate is very low (<5%). This cement offers higher resistance to chloride ions, they minimize the corrosion of the steel, and also sulfate resistance Portland cement provides higher level performance under acidic and sulfate environments. It also exhibits greater workability and pumpability.

Kuhl cement is a type of Portland cement that contains low silica and high alumina and iron oxide content. Its strength corresponds to the rapid hardening Portland cement.

Non-shrinking cement expands slightly on the hardening or has no shrinkage on subsequent air drying; they stay the same size as the volume of its initial. They don't shrink during drying.

Air-entrained Portland cement is produced by adding an air-entraining agent to Portland cement or Portland blast-furnace cement during grinding.

The variety of Portland cement is produced worldwide according to their purpose by changing the composition of cement. As a result of the broad use of cement, cement plants are world widely distributed. Lafarge Holcim-Switzerland, Anhui conch cement-China, CNBM-China, Heidelberg cement-Germany, Cemex-Mexico, Italcementi-Italy, China Resources cement-China, Taiwan

cement-Taiwan, Eurocement-Russia, Votorantim group-Brazil, are best examples for world cement plant distribution.

In Sri Lanka, there are lots of companies that fulfill the demand of cement. Such as Tokyo cement company(Lanka)PLC, Ultratech cement Lanka, The Ramco cement Limited, Mahaweli Marine cement(private)limited, Ruhunu Lanka cement (Pvt) Ltd, INSEE city cement, etc. these companies fulfill cement demand by manufacturing and importing. As a result of importation, Sri Lanka becomes the fourth country that fulfills its cement demand by importing. But from the beginning to now, Sri Lanka manufactured some amount of cement.

The first cement factory in Sri Lanka was started in Kankesanthurai. The second factory is in Puttalam. During the past war, the KanKesanthurai cement factory was closed. But the Puttalam cement factory is still working.

There are two types of factors that influence the determined location of the industry. Those are Geographical factors and non-geographical factors. Raw materials, power, labor, transport, market, water, site, and climate are taken as geographical factors. Capital, government policies, Industrial inertia, efficient organization, banking facilities, and insurance are taken as non-geographical factors. These factors depend on the behavior of inside and outside members of the company. Therefore, these factors are referred to as non-geographical factors.

Raw materials are primary materials that are used in the production process. In the cement industry, raw materials are three types. Those are, the calcareous component containing raw materials, the Argillaceous component containing raw materials, and the setting time controlling raw materials. limestones, marble, chalk, marl, coral, aragonite, oyster and clam shells, travertine, and tuff examples for calcareous substances. Limestone, shale, marl, and marble are broadly used as calcareous substances containing raw materials, to become less environmental pollution and economically friendly. These raw materials are mainly composed of CaCO_3 . In Sri Lanka CaCO_3 requirement for the cement industry is fulfilled by limestones.

The limestone requirement for the cement industry in Sri Lanka is fulfilled by the Aruwakkalu quarry. In the Aruwakkalu quarry, limestone is obtained by digging until 35-70 feet. After they make holes and take samples and analyze them. If the sample quality is enough to produce cement, they explode and acquire limestone (CaCO_3). After these limestones are transported to the factory by using the train. Mainly dolomite obtained from Kandy and Matale area laterite obtained from Andigama, in Anamaduwa. Gypsum is obtained from saltern and imports.

Dolomite is $\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$. Within heating, they decomposed into CaO and MgO . When the clinker contains 2-5% of MgO , the strength development of the cement is improved, and the setting time is shortened. Laterite is composed of a high amount of Aluminium and iron. It facilitates the formation of Tricalcium aluminate and brownmillerite. Silica is not added as raw material because it is already presented with raw materials.

After collecting these raw materials, following a dry process, raw materials grind together and make a homogeneous mixture. After grinding they are stored in silo. After storing silo chambers, a homogeneous mixture enters the cyclone preheater. After the rotary kiln. In a rotary kiln, this homogeneous mixture received 1400°C heat. The final product of kiln processing is clinker. This clinker enters a clinker cooler and is stored in storage. Finally, this clinker grind with gypsum and other mineral components produces cement. as the final step, cement packing into bags and distributed islandwide.

Within the cement industry, some problems arose. The cement industry supports environmental pollution mainly in three ways. Those are soil pollution, water pollution, and air

pollution. Solid waste is mainly due to kiln dust and cement dust. The kiln dust is mainly due to non-reactive raw materials. Some of the dust is recycled in the cement manufacturing process. Some dust can't return to the production process. That dust is used for landfilling, although some are also sold for beneficial reuse.

Another solid waste is cement dust. Cement dust is mainly deposited around the factory. These cement dust caused alkaline water and facilitated the formation of aggregates. And cement dust deposits on plants around the factory. It causes a decrease in photosynthesis. And also caused respiratory problems.

Water pollution is less in cement manufacturing. But the cement can be dissolved with rainwater and can be added to water sources. Due to the high pH value, water ecosystems can pollute.

Air pollution is the main environmental problem in the cement industry. Oxides of nitrogen, Sulphur dioxide, organic compounds, hydrogen fluoride, hydrogen chloride, and carbon monoxide are the main air pollutants. In the cement industry, there is carbon dioxide production in large amounts. The large excess amount of CO₂ is referred to as an air pollutant.

NO_x and SO_x are formed as the result of combustion. The sulfur and its components such as SO₃²⁻ are present in the raw materials. These compounds react with oxygen under high temperatures and produce SO₂.

NO_x is mainly due to the nitrogen and oxygen reactions. Nitrogen and Oxygen react under high temperatures and produce NO_x. but under normal room temperature, they do not react with each other.

The number of varieties of organic compounds is present in raw materials due to decomposition and microorganism activities. These organic compounds evaporate.

And also, the halogens present in the soil evaporate as HCl and HF. The carbon monoxide forms due to incomplete combustion.

A large amount of carbon dioxide forms due to the calcium of limestones. These gases release into the atmosphere and can cause acid rain. Therefore, the management of these pollutants must be important.

In the cement industry, solid and gas pollution is problematic compared to water pollution. Water pollution occurs in less amounts in the cement industry due to the use of less water in production processes. The solid (dust) gas pollution causes health effects and environmental effects. Chronic obstructive lung disease, pneumoconiosis, restrictive lung disease, lung function impairment, etc.

The decrease of photosynthetic ability, acid rain and the halogen gases such as HCl, HF, and CFC cause damage to the ozone layer. SO₂, and NO_x, cause photochemical smog, etc. as results of these problems, pollutant management is essential.

The use of high-quality raw materials and fuel is the best way to reduce pollution. In some cement plants, they produce burning flame in the kiln using coal. The low-quality coal is typically contaminated with sulfur and its compounds. Within burning this sulfur forms its oxides (SO₂). Therefore, high-quality fuel consumption is very important. Plant optimization is another strategy to improve the quality of production and minimize environmental pollution. In this case, we can optimize the kiln. We can control the air entering the kiln and trap the emission gases. These

trapping gases can bubble through the basic medium such as NaOH, and KOH. Or we can release them into the deep ocean.

The dust collection systems are the best method used in Sri Lanka to reduce solid waste (particulate waste). These dust collection systems are used in different sections of the cement plant. Cyclone separators, electrostatic precipitators (ESP), by filtration for removal and recycling arrangements for dust are used in cement plants. This dust collection occurs according to the dust load, particle size distribution, bulk density, and electrical resistivity. Dust removal devices come in the form of bag filters and cyclone separators. In a cyclone separator, the separation occurs by rotating gas flow. Particles are removed from the furnace gases by electrostatic precipitators or fabric bag collectors. The bag filter system is one of the efficient dust removal methods in the Sri Lankan cement industry. Cement plants minimize their pollution following the above methods. We can minimize the pollution while quarry processing, pits refills, and plants are planted in Sri Lanka. This industry will help to develop the country.

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